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SICILIAN NATURALISTIC NEWS:

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14 *Sciapus platypterus*; 15 *Myopa picta*; 16 *Diaea dorsata*; 17 *Franklinothrips megalops*;
18 *Dasyhelea bilineata*; 19 *Forcipomyia (Synthridomyia) murina*;
20 *Forcipomyia (Euprojoannisia) psilonota*; 21 *Incertana drepanensis*.

How to contribute

1. Please download from the site www.ssn.it the form (word document) and compile it
2. Send it in .doc format to salvatore.surdo@unipa.it
3. Colour photos to enrich the observation reports are welcome. When sending a photo, be sure that you have rights to publish it. Photos will have a small format, so choose it considering that the subject must be clearly visible even in this case.

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Key words: Hymenoptera Diapriidae, Diptera Mycetophilidae, Empididae, Dolichopodidae, Conopidae, Ceratopogonidae, Araneae Thomisidae, Thysanoptera Aeolothripidae, Orthoptera Tettigoniidae.

11) *Aclista alticollis* (Thomson, 1859) (Hymenoptera Diapriidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 (housed in collection of Angelo Ditta)

Site location: Bosco di Alcamo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 1.III.2021

Records validated by: Jan Macek

Reasons of interest: This is the first record from Sicily.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaeur.org>;

<http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>

Aclista alticollis, Private collection of A. Ditta, 1.III.2021 (Photo A. Ditta)

Authors' Addresses — A. DITTA, via Trieste,16 – 91026 Mazara del Vallo (Trapani); J. MACEK, Entomologické oddělení Národního muzea, Cirkusová, 1740 - 19300 Praha 9 (Czech Republic)

12) *Mycomya (Mycomya) prominens*, (Lundström, 1913) (Diptera Mycetophilidae)

Source: Facebook group Ditteri italiani
<https://www.facebook.com/groups/Ditteri/permalink/2322355171222020/>
Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area
Number of individuals: 1 (housed in collection of Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)
Site location: Nature Reserve Preola Lake and Gorgi Tondi (Trapani)
Date of observation: 5.I.2021
Records validated by Paul Beuk
Reasons of interest: This is the first record from Sicily.
Resource link: <http://www.faunaeur.org>;
<http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>

Mycomya (Mycomya) prominens, Collection Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht, 5.I.2021 (Photo A. Ditta)

Authors' Addresses — A. DITTA, Via Trieste, 16 – 91026 Mazara del Vallo (Trapani); P.L.T. BEUK, Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht, De Bosquetplein, 6-7 – NL 6211KJ Maastricht

13) *Empis (Leptempis) confusa*, Loew, 1865 (Diptera Empididae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 female (housed in collection of Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: Nature Reserve Preola Lake and Gorgi Tondi (Trapani)

Date of observation: 23.V.2020

Records validated by Paul Beuk

Reasons of interest: This is the first record from Sicily.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaeur.org>;
<http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>

Empis (Leptempis) confusa, Collection Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht, 23.V.2020 (Photo A. Ditta)

Authors' Addresses — A. DITTA, via Trieste,16 – 91026 Mazara del Vallo (Trapani);
P.L.T. BEUK, Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht, De Bosquetplein, 6-7 – NL 6211KJ Maastricht

14) *Sciapus platypterus*, (Fabricius, 1805) (Diptera Dolichopodidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 female (housed in collection of Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht)

Site location: Nature Reserve Preola Lake and Gorgi Tondi (Trapani)

Date of observation: 15.V.2021

Records validated by Paul Beuk

Reasons of interest: This is the first record from Sicily.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaeur.org>;
<http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>

Sciapus platypterus, Collection Natuurhistorisch Museum Maastricht, 15.V.2021 (Photo A. Ditta)

15) *Myopa picta* Panzer, 1797 (Diptera Conopidae)

Source: Facebook group Ditteri italiani

<https://m.facebook.com/groups/Ditteri/permalink/2577906669000201/>

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 male and 1 female (housed in collection of D. Clements)

Site location: Nature Reserve Preola Lake and Gorghetti Tondi (Trapani)

Date of observation: 18.IV.2021

Records validated by Marcello Consolo

Reasons of interest: This is the first record from Sicily.

Resource link: <http://www.faunaeur.org>;

<http://www.faunaitalia.it/checklist/>

References

CHVALA M. & SMITH K.G.V., 1988. Conopidae. In: Soos, A. & Papp, L. (Eds.) Catalogue of Palearctic Diptera. Vol. 8. *Elsevier*, Amsterdam-Oxford-New York-Tokyo, 363 pp.

RIVOSECCHI L., 1996. Chiavi analitiche illustrate sui Conopidae (Diptera) della Fauna Italiana. *Boll. Mus. civ. St. nat. Verona*, 20: 135-151.

Myopa picta, Nature Reserve Preola Lake and Gorghetti Tondi (Trapani), 18.IV.2021 (Photo A. Ditta)

Authors' Addresses — A. DITTA, Via Trieste, 16 – 91026 Mazara del Vallo (Trapani); M. CONSOLO, via Piemonte, 16/b – 35127 Padova.

16) *Diaea dorsata* (Fabricius, 1777) (Araneae Thomisidae)

Source: Author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1

Site location: Monte Salto del Cane, Pedara (Catania)

Date of observation: 9.VIII.2017

Notes of the observer: an adult male (housed in collection of A. Dentici)

Records validated by Antonino Dentici

Reasons of interest: This is the first record of Genus and species for Sicily (PANTINI & ISAIA, 2019).

Reference

PANTINI P. & ISAIA M., 2019. Araneae.it: the online Catalog of Italian spiders with addenda on other Arachnid Orders occurring in Italy (Arachnida: Araneae, Opiliones, Palpigradi, Pseudoscorpionida, Scorpiones, Solifugae). *Fragmenta Entomologica*, 51(2): 127-152. Online at www.araneae.it, accessed on {10.09.2022}.

Authors' Addresses — A. DENTICI, Via E. Cialdini, 2 - 90124 Palermo (I); E. GIARRUSSO, Department of Agriculture, Food and Environment (Di3A) University of Catania.

17) *Franklinothrips megalops* Trybom, 1912 (Thysanoptera Aeolothripidae)

Source: Author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1

Site location: River Mazaro, Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 9.I.2021

Notes of the observer: an adult female (housed in collection of G. Degabriele)

Records validated by Rita Marullo

Reasons of interest: This is the first record of Genus and species for Italy.

References

MARULLO R. & DE GRAZIA A., 2013. Territorial distribution, classification and relationships amongst Italian Thysanoptera. *Bulletin of Insectology*, 66 (1): 127-134.

MARULLO R. & DE GRAZIA A., 2015. The introduced species over the last twenty years in the Italian Thrips Fauna. *Die Bodenkultur*, Wien, 66 (3-4): 27-31.

Franklinothrips megalops, Private collection G. Degabriele, 9.I.2021 (leg. Angelo Ditta)

Authors' Addresses — A. DITTA, via Trieste, 16 – 91026 Mazara del Vallo (Trapani); R. MARULLO, Department of Agricultural Sciences, Università degli Studi Mediterranea di Reggio Calabria, Località Feo di Vito - 89060 Reggio Calabria (I).

18) *Dasyhelea bilineata* Goetghebuer, 1920 (Diptera Ceratopogonidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 14 female and 14 male (housed in collection of Patrycja Dominiak)

Site location: Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 24.XII.2020 (1f); 24.XII.2021 (1m); 23 (2m & 1f), 24 (2f), 26 (1m) and 28.II.2022 (1m); 3 (1f), 5 (1f), 6 (3f), 13 (3m & 1f), 15 (1m) and 25.III.2022 (1f); 5 (2m & 1 f) and 14.IV.2022 (1m & 2f); 4.V.2022 (2 m)

Notes of the observer: specimen sent to Patrycja Dominiak for identification

Records validated by Patrycja Dominiak

Reasons of interest: This is the first record for Sicily. In Italy the species is reported from Caserta with the synonym *D. saxicola* (SZADZIEWSKI & DOMINIAK, 2006; DOMINIAK & SZADZIEWSKI, 2010) and with the synonym *D. tecticola* (SANNINO & ESPINOSA, 2004).

Dasyhelea bilineata female abdomen. Private collection Patrycja Dominiak, 24.XII.2020 (leg. Angelo Ditta)

References

- DOMINIAK P. & SZADZIEWSKI R., 2010. Distribution and new synonymy in European biting midges of the genus *Dasyhelea* Kieffer (Diptera: Ceratopogonidae). Vol. 2437 (1). <https://doi.org/10.11646/zootaxa.2437.1.1>
- SANNINO L. & ESPINOSA B., 2004. The ceratopogonid *Dasyhelea tecticola* Remmert (Diptera, Nematocera) new for Italy damages tobacco in seedbed. *Informatore Fitopatologico*, 3: 32-34.

SZADZIEWSKI R. & DOMINIAK P., 2006. New synonyms of European Ceratopogonidae (Diptera). *Annales Zoologici*, 56: 139-146.

Authors' Addresses — A. DITTA, via Trieste,16 – 91026 Mazara del Vallo (TP); P. DOMINIAK, UiT - Tromsø Museum, Lars Thørings vei, 10 - 9006 TROMSØ (Norvegia)

19) *Forcipomyia (Synthridomyia) murina* (Winnertz, 1852) (Diptera Ceratopogonidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 1 male (housed in collection of Patrycja Dominiak)

Site location: Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 23.II.2022

Notes of the observer: specimen sent to Patrycja Dominiak for identification

Records validated by Patrycja Dominiak

Forcipomyia murina male genitalia Private collection Patrycja Dominiak, 23.II.2022 (leg. Angelo Ditta)

Reasons of interest: This is the first record for Sicily (NAVAI & SZADZIEWSKI, 2016).

Reference

NAVAI S. & SZADZIEWSKI R., 2016. Biting modges of the genus *Forcipomyia* Meigen (Diptera: Ceratopogonidae). *Studia Dipterologica*, 21: 65-95.

Authors' Addresses — A. DITTA, via Trieste,16 – 91026 Mazara del Vallo (Trapani); P. DOMINIAK, UiT - Tromsø Museum, Lars Thørings vei, 10 - 9006 TROMSØ (Norvegia)

20) *Forcipomyia (Euprojoannisia) psilonota* (Kieffer, 1911) (Diptera Ceratopogonidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Number of individuals: 3 male (housed in collection of Patrycja Dominiak)

Site location: Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 15.I.2021; 26.II.2022 (2m)

Forcipomyia psilonota male genitalia Private collection Patrycja Dominiak, 15.I.2021 (leg. Angelo Ditta)

Notes of the observer: specimen sent to Patrycja Dominiak for identification

Records validated by Patrycja Dominiak

Reasons of interest: This is the first record for Sicily.

References

ALWIN-KOWNACKA A., SZADZIEWSKI R. & SZWEDO J., 2016. Biting midges of the subfamily *Forcipomyiinae* (Diptera: Ceratopogonidae) from the Middle East, with keys and descriptions of new species. *Zootaxa*, 4173(4): 351-378. doi: 10.11646/zootaxa.4173.4.2. PMID: 27811827.

FOXI C., CONTINI C. & DELRIO G., 2018. Contribution to the knowledge of biting midges (Diptera Ceratopogonidae) of Sardinia, Italy. *Redia*, 101: 137-141.

Authors' Addresses — A. DITTA, via Trieste,16 – 91026 Mazara del Vallo (Trapani); P. DOMINIAK, UiT - Tromsø Museum, Lars Thørings vei 10 - 9006 TROMSØ (Norvegia).

21) *Incertana drepanensis* (Massa, Fontana & Buzzetti, 2006) (Orthoptera Tettigoniidae)

Source: author

Category: Species of unusual occurrence for a given area

Incertana drepanensis female, 8.IX.2021 (leg. Angelo Ditta)

Number of individuals: 1 female (housed in collection of B. Massa)

Site location: Contrada Santa Maria - Mazara del Vallo (Trapani)

Date of observation: 8.IX.2021 (f); 20.VIII.2022 (m)

Notes of the observer: specimens identified by Bruno Massa

Records validated by Bruno Massa

Reasons of interest: The species is reported for Sicily only from three localities. It is the fourth locality for this local endemism. The observation took place next to a stream suggesting a predilection by this species for humid environments.

Author's Address — A. DITTA, via Trieste,16 – 91026 Mazara del Vallo (Trapani).

